

Status of Implementation of Inclusive Education Schemes for Students with Intellectual Disabilities in the State of Kerala

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Abstract

Inclusive education (IE) advancement in the twenty-first century has given access to top-notch education a given for all students globally. IE has evolved to the point where it can now accommodate all students, offer appropriate education, and satisfy the academic needs of both challenged and non-disabled children. This study briefly examines the development of IE for students with intellectual disabilities (SwIDs) and some of the implementation challenges. Including all SwIDs in regular classrooms is the aim of inclusive education, but several challenges must be overcome for their education to be successful. The inclusion of the SwIDs highlights both the child's right to attend school and the responsibility of the school to accept the student. It urges changing from the current system, which assigns SwIDs depending on their maturity level, to one that promotes experience and maturity that enhances SwIDs learning. Moreover, it provides a structure for a curriculum that can be modified from the current standard curriculum. The proposed model needs to be evaluated in practical use. The study aims to discover how IE is used in Kerala to carry out various initiatives and processes. For children with and without disabilities, the central government has financed various programs in schooling and mobility management. However, the objective of the current study is to ascertain how the Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan (SMSA) and the Assistance to Disabled Persons Scheme (ADIP), two initiatives, are being carried out. A descriptive survey research technique was used, and fourteen districts in Kerala obtained 500 samples. The sample was chosen using the non-probability and purposeful sampling methods. Using a rating scale that the researcher designed, the data was gathered from respondents and then appropriately statistically evaluated and interpreted. The findings of the present research study revealed that it includes the level of awareness, availability, accessibility and advantages among headteachers | headmistresses, general educators, special educators, paraprofessionals and parents under inclusive education schemes for students with intellectual disabilities are average. The present study will contribute to the current research in inclusive education schemes and support to uphold the meaningful reintegration of SwIDs. It also looks forward to future research studies to draw and shape the present study by overwhelming its limitations.

Keywords: Implementation, Students with intellectual disability, Inclusive Education Schemes

Introduction

Including children with disabilities is about the child's right to participate, and it is the teachers' responsibility to accept the child. Integrating children with disabilities into mainstream classroom settings is one of the largest problems afflicting the educational system nationally and internationally (Sharma et al., 2008). Inclusion is the most effective method for developing social skills in children with and without impairments. Addressing social stigma, upholding the rights of each learner, promoting staff collaboration, and enabling students with special needs to participate in regular activities and exhibit their potential are all goals of an inclusive approach (Hayden & Thompson, 2000). Students with disabilities should get special consideration, but all students should participate in class (National Curriculum Framework, 2005). In many nations where IE is the norm, an increasing proportion of children with special needs (SEN) attend inclusive classrooms alongside children without SEN (Wehmeyer & Shogren, 2017). Children without special educational needs usually interact with

SwIDs in inclusive classes or special education settings (Kauffman et al., 2017). While special education support is required in both circumstances, they are very different from one another (Florian, 2019; Zigmond & Kloo, 2017). Since IE for SwIDs has been praised by several nations, IE is still uncommon. Knowledge of the definitions of inclusion and intellectual disability from the theoretical point of view would enhance cross-cultural collaboration and make practice adaptation easier. The inclusion of SwID is still less common than the inclusion of students with learning disabilities, language disorders, or behavioral issues (Göransson et al., 2020; Wehmeyer, Shogren, and Kurth, 2021). The state of Kerala has made a better education standard possible. Kerala frequently outperforms other states regarding social growth and overall quality of life, with a proper emphasis on education.

In contrast to India, Kerala provides its citizens with free healthcare, education, help for the unemployed, and financial support for employed people. The SSA

system now has special education programs in operation. These programs will help to improve the rates of transition between the various levels of education and support the idea that every child should have the opportunity to finish their education. The state is committed to ensuring high educational standards and a high-quality education enabling our students to compete globally.

Statement of the Problem

The present study is concerned with the status of implementation of inclusive education services for individuals with intellectual disabilities in terms of awareness, availability, accessibility and advantages existing in the current scenario of the state of Kerala from the viewpoint of masters \ Headmistresses, General Educators, Special Educators and Paraprofessionals working in an inclusive setting. Therefore, the study is entitled "Status of Implementation of Inclusive Education Schemes for Students with Intellectual Disabilities in the State of Kerala."

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the awareness of Inclusive Education Schemes (IES) for the students with intellectual disabilities among the stakeholders working in the inclusive setting in the state of Kerala
2. To find out the availability of Inclusive Education Schemes (IES) implemented for the students with intellectual disabilities in the inclusive setting in the state of Kerala
3. To find out the accessibility of Inclusive Education Schemes (IES) for the students with intellectual disabilities in the inclusive setting in the state of Kerala.
4. To find out the advantages of Inclusive Education Schemes (IES) from the stakeholders responsible for providing inclusive education for the students with intellectual disabilities in the state of Kerala.

Research Questions

1. How far the headmasters \ headmistresses, general educators, special educators, paraprofessional and parents working in inclusive setting in the state of Kerala were aware about inclusive education schemes?
2. What are the inclusive education schemes (IES) available for students with intellectual disabilities in inclusive setting in the state of Kerala?
3. To what extend the inclusive education schemes (IES) are accessible for students with intellectual disabilities in inclusive setting in the state of Kerala?
4. Does the inclusive education schemes (IES) gives advantages for students with intellectual disability in point of view of headmasters \ headmistresses, general educators, special

educators, paraprofessional and parents working in inclusive setting in the state of Kerala?

Methodology

Research Design

The present study's goal is to provide a descriptive research study. The term "descriptive research" refers to a variety of fact-finding methods, including surveys. The main objective of descriptive research studies is to provide an accurate description or picture of the state, characteristics, or occurrence of a situation or event.

Sampling Technique

The sampling method is an important step in carrying out any research study. The Purposive Sampling method of the Non-Probability sampling approach was used by the Investigator to choose the sample. In fourteen districts throughout the state of Kerala, data was collected from headmasters, headmistresses, general educators, special educators, paraprofessionals, and parents of inclusive schools.

Target Population

The present study looked at how inclusive education schemes for students with intellectual disabilities are being implemented in the state of Kerala. The 14 districts that make up the State of Kerala contain the study's target population.

Sample Size

A total number of 500 samples were selected for the present study. The sample is divided into five categories.

Category	Frequency
Headmaster \ Headmistresses	100
Para- Professionals	100
General Educators	100
Special Educators	100
Parents	100
Total	500

Variables of the Study

The variables employed in the current study included like category, age, gender, educational qualification, experience, types of service, locations of school, income, types of family, socio-economic status, and employment status.

Research Tool

The usage of tools in a research study is important because they are essential for data gathering and serve as the basis for all research endeavors. Thanks to technologies, researchers may collect, establish, investigate, visualize, and share study findings. The construction of a suitable tool is essential for effective study. Numerous tools are offered to aid in the research of the problem. Each tool must function effectively for the purpose for which it was designed. In the present study, the investigator will develop the tool Rating Scale for Inclusive Education Schemes (RIES).

Data Collection

The purposive sampling technique was used by the researcher to identify the sample. For the present research, a total of 500 samples were chosen from fourteen districts in the state of Kerala. In order to more fully accomplish the investigation's objectives, the present study's data collection procedure was divided into four stages.

Data Analysis

The responses to the data collected were counted and compiled. The variables and research aims of the current study were analyzed using a variety of descriptive and statistical techniques supported by the Spss package. The collected data was examined and examined using data analysis tools.

Analysis of Demographic Control Variables

This section analysed the influence of demographic control variables, that is, category, type of school, educational qualification, gender,

experience, age, salary, locations of school, types of family, socio-economic status and employment status on Awareness, Availability, Accessibility and Advantages on the Inclusive Education Schemes (IES) for the student's intellectual disabilities among stakeholders working in inclusive setting in the state of Kerala. The analyses were conducted using independent sample Z test or one-way ANOVA. A one-sample analysis of variance is used to test hypotheses about means when there are three or more groups of one independent variable.

Category

Table 1.1 Category-wise frequency level of headmasters | headmistresses, paraprofessionals, special educators, general educators, and parents

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Headmaster	100	20.0
Para Professionals	100	20.0
Special educators	100	20.0
General educators	100	20.0
Parents	100	20.0
Total	500	100.0

Figure No. 4.1Category-wise frequency level of samples

In this case, category was considered to be the independent variable, which included five groups (a) Headmaster \ Headmistress (b) Para-Professionals (c) Special educators (d) General educators (e) Parents.

So, ANOVA was used to compare the mean scores of different category of respondents and the result is exhibited in Table: 1.1.

Table: 1.2 Means, standard deviation and F value for category

Variables	Category	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	F	P value
Awareness	Headmaster\ Headmistress	100	22.13	6.22	7.435	<0.001
	Para Professionals	100	22.32	5.51		
	Special educators	100	23.39	7.80		
	General educators	100	24.79	6.36		
	Parents	100	26.46	7.19		
Availability	Headmaster\ Headmistress	100	22.78	6.34	2.151	<0.001
	Para Professionals	100	22.84	6.96		
	Special educators	100	24.19	7.86		
	General educators	100	24.19	6.97		
	Parents	100	25.34	8.31		
Accessibility	Headmaster\ Headmistress	100	20.14	7.36	7.784	<0.001
	Para Professionals	100	20.12	5.97		
	Special educators	100	21.23	7.24		
	General educators	100	22.67	6.79		
	Parents	100	24.83	8.13		
Advantages	Headmaster\ Headmistress	100	21.54	6.63	5.877	<0.001
	Para Professionals	100	21.05	5.63		
	Special educators	100	22.11	7.37		
	General educators	100	24.29	6.67		
	Parents	100	24.63	7.25		

Interpretation

The results of the ANOVA test depicted in Table: 1.2 revealed that the statistical value of p is less than 0.05 the variables Awareness, Accessibility and Advantages. So we concluded that the mean score

of Awareness, Accessibility and Advantages differed with category. But in the case of Availability no significant difference was observed between different categories as the p value was more than 0.05.

Table: 1.3 Multiple Comparison Tests

Dependent Variable		Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	
Awareness	Headmaster Headmistress	Para Professionals	-0.190	0.942	0.840
		Special educators	-1.260	0.942	0.182
		General educators	-2.66000*	0.942	0.005
		Parents	-4.33000*	0.942	0.000
	Para Professionals	Headmaster Headmistress	0.190	0.942	0.840
		Special educators	-1.070	0.942	0.257
		General educators	-2.47000*	0.942	0.009
		Parents	-4.14000*	0.942	0.000
	Special educators	Headmaster\ Headmistress	1.260	0.942	0.182
		Para Professionals	1.070	0.942	0.257
		General educators	-1.400	0.942	0.138
		Parents	-3.07000*	0.942	0.001
	General educators	Headmaster\ Headmistress	2.66000*	0.942	0.005
		Para Professionals	2.47000*	0.942	0.009
		Special educators	1.400	0.942	0.138
		Parents	-1.670	0.942	0.077
	Parents	Headmaster\ Headmistress	4.33000*	0.942	0.000

Dependent Variable		Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.		
		Headmistress				
		Para Professionals	4.14000*	0.942	0.000	
		Special educators	3.07000*	0.942	0.001	
		General educators	1.670	0.942	0.077	
Accessibility	Headmaster Headmistress	Para Professionals	0.020	1.009	0.984	
		Special educators	-1.090	1.009	0.280	
		General educators	-2.53000*	1.009	0.012	
		Parents	-4.69000*	1.009	0.000	
	Para Professionals	Headmaster Headmistress	-0.020	1.009	0.984	
		Special educators	-1.110	1.009	0.272	
		General educators	-2.55000*	1.009	0.012	
		Parents	-4.71000*	1.009	0.000	
	Special educators	Headmaster Headmistress	1.090	1.009	0.280	
		Para Professionals	1.110	1.009	0.272	
		General educators	-1.440	1.009	0.154	
		Parents	-3.60000*	1.009	0.000	
	General educators	Headmaster	2.53000*	1.009	0.012	
		Para Professionals	2.55000*	1.009	0.012	
		Special educators	1.440	1.009	0.154	
		Parents	-2.16000*	1.009	0.033	
	Parents	Headmaster Headmistress	4.69000*	1.009	0.000	
		Para Professionals	4.71000*	1.009	0.000	
		Special educators	3.60000*	1.009	0.000	
		General educators	2.16000*	1.009	0.033	
	Advantages	Headmaster\ Headmistress	Para Professionals	0.490	0.953	0.607
			Special educators	-0.570	0.953	0.550
			General educators	-2.75000*	0.953	0.004
			Parents	-3.09000*	0.953	0.001
		Para Professionals	Headmaster Headmistress	-0.490	0.953	0.607
			Special educators	-1.060	0.953	0.266
			General educators	-3.24000*	0.953	0.001
			Parents	-3.58000*	0.953	0.000
Special educators		Headmaster Headmistress	0.570	0.953	0.550	
		Para Professionals	1.060	0.953	0.266	
		General educators	-2.18000*	0.953	0.023	
		Parents	-2.52000*	0.953	0.008	
General educators		Headmaster\ Headmistress	2.75000*	0.953	0.004	
		Para Professionals	3.24000*	0.953	0.001	
		Special educators	2.18000*	0.953	0.023	
		Parents	-0.340	0.953	0.721	
Parents		Headmaster\ Headmistress	3.09000*	0.953	0.001	
		Para Professionals	3.58000*	0.953	0.000	
		Special educators	2.52000*	0.953	0.008	
		General educators	0.340	0.953	0.721	

The significant difference existed in the groups is indicated by (*).

Interpretation

Since the ANOVA test indicated that significant difference exists among the categories for Awareness, Accessibility and Advantages, We conducted post hoc test or multiple comparison test to identify which among the categories differed

significantly and the result is exhibited in the Table: 1.3. The result of the analysis indicated that for Awareness, Parents differ significantly with every other category of respondents. Significant difference was seen between General educators, Headmasters \ Headmistresses and Para professionals. The difference between the groups is indicated by (*)

Table: 1.4. Age frequency and percentage levels of samples

Age	Frequency	Percent
Up to 30 Years	84	16.8
31-40 Years	156	31.2
Above 40 Years	260	52.
Total	500	100.0

Figure: 1.2 Age wise frequency level of samples

A one sample analysis of variance was used to test hypotheses. In this case, age of respondents was considered to be the independent variable, which

included three age groups (a) Below 30 years (b) 31-40years (c) Above 40 years. So ANOVA was used to compare the mean scores of different age groups and the result is exhibited in Table 1.4.

Table No.1.5. Means, standard deviation and F value for age

Variables	Age	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	F	P value
Awareness	Up to 30 Years	84	24.54	6.63	0.578	0.562
	31- 40 Years	156	23.76	6.43		
	Above 40 Years	260	23.62	7.14		
Availability	Up to 30 Years	84	24.71	7.60	0.673	0.511
	31- 40 Years	156	23.65	6.87		
	Above 40 Years	260	23.73	7.57		
Accessibility	Up to 30 Years	84	22.88	7.10	1.153	0.316
	31- 40 Years	156	21.72	6.71		
	Above 40 Years	260	21.49	7.73		
Advantage	Up to 30 Years	84	23.14	7.25	0.297	0.743
	31-40 Years	156	22.44	6.40		
	Above 40 Years	260	22.76	7.03		

Interpretation

The results of the ANOVA test depicted in Table: 1.5 reveal that the statistical value of p was more

than 0.05 for all the variables. So we concluded that the mean score of Awareness, Availability, Accessibility and Advantages didn't differ with age groups.

Gender

Table: 1.6 Gender frequency and percentage levels of samples

Gender	Frequency	Percept
Male	116	23.2
Female	384	76.8
Total	500	100.0

Figure: 1.3 Gender wise frequency level of samples

An independent sample Z test was often used to compare the mean scores of variables the two

different groups, that is, males and females. Hence a Z test was conducted, and the results are shown in Table: 1.6

Table: 1.7 Mean, standard deviation and Z value for gender

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Z	P value
Awareness	Male	116	24.42	7.00	1.087	0.277
	Female	384	24.64	8.07		
Availability	Male	116	24.08	8.07	0.350	0.727
	Female	384	23.80	7.14		
Accessibility	Male	116	22.30	7.15	0.845	0.399
	Female	384	21.65	7.38		
Advantage	Male	116	23.55	6.76	1.483	0.139
	Female	384	22.47	6.89		

Interpretation

The result showed that significant difference existed between males and females for all the variables as the p value in this case was less than 0.05.

Location of School

Table: 1.8 Location of school frequency and percentage levels of samples

Location of School	Frequency	Percent
Urban	181	36.2
Semi Urban	114	22.8
Rural	205	41,0
Total	500	100.0

Figure: 1.4 Location of school wise frequency level of samples

A one sample analysis of variance was used to test hypotheses means when there are three or more groups of one independent variable. In this case, location of school was considered to be the independent variable, which included localities (a)

Urban (b) Semi urban (c) Rural. So ANOVA was used to compare the mean scores of different locality of schools and the result is exhibited in Table: 1.7.

Table: 1.8 Means, standard deviation and F value for location of school

Variables	Location of school	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	F	P value
Awareness	Urban	181	24.97	7.68	4.765	0.009
	Semi Urban	114	23.75	5.62		
	Rural	205	22.84	6.52		
Availability	Urban	181	24.49	7.68	3.505	0.031
	Semi Urban	114	24.74	7.61		
	Rural	205	22.83	6.82		
Accessibility	Urban	181	22.38	8.23	1.689	0.186
	Semi Urban	114	22.17	6.41		
	Rural	205	21.08	6.91		
Advantage	Urban	181	23.43	7.62	3.596	0.028
	Semi Urban	114	23.38	6.45		
	Rural	205	21.74	6.28		

Interpretation

The results of the ANOVA test depicted in Table: 1.8 revealed that the statistical value of p was less than 0.05, for the variables Awareness, Availability and Advantages. So we concluded that the mean score of Awareness, Availability and

Advantages differed with location of school. But in the case of Accessibility no significant difference was observed between the schools situated in different localities as the p value was more than 0.05.

Table: 1.9 Multiple comparison tests

Dependent Variable		Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	
Awareness	Urban	Semi Urban	1.227	0.811	0.131
		Rural	2.13335*	0.692	0.002
	Semi Urban	Urban	-1.227	0.811	0.131
		Rural	0.907	0.792	0.253
	Rural	Urban	-2.13335*	0.692	0.002
		Semi Urban	-0.907	0.792	0.253

Dependent Variable		Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	
Availability	Urban	Semi Urban	-0.245	0.875	0.780
		Rural	1.65757*	0.747	0.027
	Semi Urban	Urban	0.747	0.875	0.780
		Rural	1.90270*	0.855	0.027
	Rural	Urban	-1.65757*	0.747	0.027
		Semi Urban	-1.90270*	0.855	0.027
Advantage	Urban	Semi Urban	0.048	0.817	0.953
		Rural	1.68395*	0.697	0.016
	Semi Urban	Urban	-0.048	0.817	0.953
		Rural	1.63573*	0.953	0.041
	Rural	Urban	-1.68395*	0.697	0.016
		Semi Urban	-1.63573*	0.798	0.041

The significant difference existed in groups are indicated by (*).

Interpretation

Since the ANOVA test indicated that the significant difference existed among the schools situated in different localities for Awareness, Availability and Advantages, We conducted post hoc test or multiple comparison test for identify

which among schools differs significantly and the result is exhibited in the Table: 1.9. The result of the analysis indicated that for Awareness, significant difference is observed between schools in urban and rural localities. No difference was observed between schools located in semi urban and urban localities. The difference between the groups is indicated by (*) **Educational Qualification**

Table: 1.10 Educational qualification frequency and percentage levels of samples

Educational qualification	Frequency	Percent
Post Graduate	125	31.2
Graduate	155	38.8
Diploma	120	30
Total	400	100.0

Figure: 1.5 Educational qualification wise frequency level of samples

A one sample analysis of variance was used to test hypotheses. In this case, educational qualification was considered to be the independent variable,

which included three qualifications (a) Post Graduate (b) Graduate (c) Diploma. So ANOVA was used to compare the mean scores of different

educational qualifications and the result is exhibited in Table 1.10

Table: 1.11 Means, standard deviation and F value for educational qualification

Variables	Educational qualification	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	F	P value
Awareness	Post Graduate	125	23.38	6.44	0.284	0.753
	Graduate	155	23.27	6.77		
	Diploma	120	22.78	6.53		
Availability	Post Graduate	125	22.79	6.40	1.051	0.350
	Graduate	155	23.63	7.37		
	Diploma	120	24.08	7.30		
Accessibility	Post Graduate	125	21.01	7.09	1.269	0.282
	Graduate	155	20.47	6.60		
	Diploma	120	21.81	7.10		
Advantage	Post Graduate	125	22.03	6.30	1.450	0.236
	Graduate	155	21.76	6.69		
	Diploma	120	23.10	7.05		

Interpretation

The results of the ANOVA test depicted in Table: 1.11 revealed that the statistical value of p was more than 0.05 for all the variables. So we concluded that

the mean score of Awareness, Availability, Accessibility and Advantages didn't differ with educational qualification.

Educational Qualification of Parents

Table: 1.12 Educational qualification frequency and percentage levels of samples

Educational qualification	Frequency	Percent
Literate	90	90
Illiterate	10	10
Total	100	100

Figure: 1.6 Educational qualification wise frequency level of samples

An independent sample Z test was often used to compare the mean scores of variables the two different groups, that is, Literate and Illiterate

respondents. Hence a Z test was conducted, and the results are shown in Table: 1.12.

Table: 1.13 Means, standard deviation and z value for educational qualification

Variables	Educational qualification	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Z	P value
Awareness	Literate	90	26.89	7.08	1.811	0.073
	Illiterate	10	22.60	7.38		
Availability	Literate	90	25.92	8.24	2.139	0.035*
	Illiterate	10	20.10	7.40		
Accessibility	Literate	90	25.03	8.34	0.748	0.456
	Illiterate	10	23.00	5.93		
Advantage	Literate	90	24.90	7.47	1.119	0.266
	Illiterate	10	22.20	4.24		

Significant

Interpretation

The result showed that no significant difference existed between Literate and Illiterate respondents for the variables Awareness, Accessibility and

Type of School

Advantages as the p value in this case was more than 0.05. But in the case of Availability since the p value was less than 0.05, significant difference was seen between Literate and Illiterate respondents.

Table: 1.13. Type of School frequency and percentage levels of samples

Type of school	Frequency	Percent
Govt. Aided	88	22
Government	33	8.2
Private	279	69.8
Total	400	100.0

Figure: 1.7 Type of school wise frequency level of samples

A one sample analysis of variance was used to test hypotheses about means when there are three or more groups of one independent variable. In this case, type of school was considered to be the independent

variable, which included three types (a) Govt. Aided (b) Government (c) Private schools. So ANOVA was used to compare the mean scores of different type of schools and the result is exhibited in Table: 1.13.

Table: 1.14. Means, standard deviation and F value for type of school

Variables	Types of school	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p value
Awareness	Govt. Aided	88	23.83	5.45	0.589	0.555
	Government	33	22.88	6.38		
	Private	279	22.98	6.94		
Availability	Govt. Aided	88	23.17	6.65	0.215	0.806
	Government	33	23.09	6.95		
	Private	279	23.65	7.22		
Accessibility	Govt. Aided	88	20.85	3.85	0.021	0.979
	Government	33	21.08	7.04		
	Private	279		6.44		
Advantage	Govt. Aided	88	22.39	7.16	0.602	0.548
	Government	33	23.39	4.97		
	Private	279	22.07	6.73		

Interpretation

The results of the ANOVA test depicted in Table: 1.14 revealed that the statistical value of p is more than 0.05 for all the variables. So we concluded that the mean score of Awareness, Availability, Accessibility and Advantages didn't differ with Location of school.

Table: 1.15 Multiple comparison tests

Dependent Variable			Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Awareness	Govt. Aided	Government	-0.225	0.916	0.806
		Private	1.79651*	0.740	0.016
	Government	Govt. Aided	0.225	0.916	0.806
		Private	2.02151*	0.787	0.011
	Private	Govt. Aided	-1.79651*	0.740	0.016
		Government	-2.02151*	0.787	0.011
Accessibility	Govt. Aided	Government	-0.532	0.985	0.589
		Private	1.376	0.796	0.085
	Government	Govt. Aided	0.532	0.985	0.589
		Private	1.90766*	0.847	0.025
	Private	Govt. Aided	-1.376	0.796	0.085
		Government	-1.90766*	0.847	0.025

The significant difference existed in groups are indicated by (*).

Interpretation

Since the ANOVA test indicated that the significant difference existed among the type of schools for Awareness and Accessibility, We conducted post hoc test or multiple comparison test

for identify which among schools differs significantly and the result is exhibited in Table: 4.20. The result of the analysis indicated that for Awareness, Private schools differed significantly with Govt. Aided as well as Government schools. The difference between the groups is indicated by (*)

8. Experience

Table: 1 16. Experience frequency and percentage levels of samples

<i>Experience</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Below five years	79	19.8
5-10 years	113	28.2
Above 10 years	208	52.0
Total	400	100.0

Figure:1.8 Experience wise frequency level of samples

A one sample analysis of variance was used to test hypotheses. In this case, years of experience was considered to be the independent variable, which included three years of experience (a) Below five years (b) 5-10 years (c) Above 10 years. So

ANOVA was used to compare the mean scores of different years of experience and the result is exhibited in Table: 1.15.

Table: 1.16 Means, standard deviation and F value for experience

Variables	Experience	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	F	P value
Awareness	Below five years	79	24.51	7.00	2.667	0.071
	5-10 years	113	23.36	6.41		
	Above 10 years	208	22.53	6.47		
Availability	Below five years	79	25.08	7.67	2.745	0.065
	5-10 years	113	23.50	6.70		
	Above 10 years	208	22.90	6.95		
Accessibility	Below five years	79	21.99	6.49	3.410	0.034
	5-10 years	113	21.96	6.61		
	Above 10 years	208	20.18	7.15		
Advantages	Below five years	79	23.38	6.97	3.633	0.027
	5-10 years	113	23.03	6.82		
	Above 10 years	208	21.39	6.43		

Interpretation

The results of the ANOVA test depicted in Table: 1.16 revealed that the statistical value of p

was less than 0.05 for the variables Accessibility and Advantages. So we concluded that the mean

score of Accessibility and Advantages differed with years of experience.

Table: 1.17 Multiple comparison tests

Dependent Variable			Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Accessibility	Below five years	5-10 years	0.023	1.008	0.982
		Above 10 years	1.80946*	0.908	0.047
	5-10 years	Below five years	-0.023	1.008	0.982
		Above 10 years	1.78672*	0.803	0.027
	Above 10 years	Below five years	-1.80946*	0.908	0.047
		5-10 years	-1.78672*	0.803	0.027
Advantages	Below five years	5-10 years	0.353	0.975	0.717
		Above 10 years	1.98552*	0.879	0.024
	5-10 years	Below five years	-0.353	0.975	0.717
		Above 10 years	1.63232*	0.777	0.036
	Above 10 years	Below five years	-1.98552*	0.879	0.024
		5-10 years	-1.63232*	0.777	0.036

The significant difference exist groups are indicated by (*).

Interpretation

Since the ANOVA test indicated that the significant difference exist among the years of experience for Accessibility and Advantages, We conducted post hoc test or multiple comparison test for identify which among years of experience differs

Income

significantly and the result is exhibited in the Table: 1.17. The result of the analysis indicated that for Accessibility, significant difference was observed between Above 10 years and Below five years as well as Above 10 years and 5-10 years. No significant difference was observed between Below five years and 5-10 years. The difference between the groups was indicated by (*).

Table No. 1.18. Income frequency and percentage levels of samples

Income	Frequency	Percent
Below 10,000	180	45.0
11,000 to 20,000	116	29.0
21,000 to 30,000	104	26.-
Total	400	100.0

Figure: 1.9 Income wise frequency level of samples

A one sample analysis of variance was used to test hypotheses. In this case, income same group was considered to be the independent variable, which

included three years' income groups (a) Below 10,000 (b) 11,000 to 20,000 (c) 21,000 to 30,000. So ANOVA was used to compare the mean scores

of different income groups and the result is exhibited in Table: 1.18.

Table: 1.19 Means, standard deviation and F value for Income

Variables	Salary	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	F	P value
Awareness	Below 10,000	180	21.74	6.32	9.305	<0.001
	11,000 to 20,000	116	23.63	6.42		
	21,000 to 30,000	104	25.09	6.71		
Availability	Below 10,000	180	23.42	6.90	1.173	0.310
	11,000 to 20,000	116	22.88	6.99		
	21,000 to 30,000	104	24.33	7.39		
Accessibility	Below 10,000	180	20.96	6.97	0.481	0.619
	11,000 to 20,000	116	20.68	6.38		
	21,000 to 30,000	104	21.58	7.41		
Advantage	Below 10,000	180	21.54	6.42	2.168	2.168
	11,000 to 20,000	116	22.47	7.01		
	21,000 to 30,000	104	23.22	6.71		

Interpretation

The results of the ANOVA test depicted in Table 1.19 revealed that the statistical value of p

was less than 0.05 for the variable Awareness. So we concluded that the mean score of Accessibility differed with age.

Table No. 1.20 Multiple comparison tests

Dependent Variable			Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Awareness	Below 10,000	11,000 to 20,000	-1.89042*	0.768	0.014
		21,000 to 30,000	-3.34765*	0.795	0.000
	11,000 to 20,000	Below 10,000	1.89042*	0.768	0.014
		21,000 to 30,000	-1.457	0.871	0.095
	21,000 to 30,000	Below 10,000	3.34765*	0.795	0.000
		11,000 to 20,000	1.457	0.871	0.095

The significant difference exist groups are indicated by (*).

Interpretation

Since the ANOVA test indicated that the significant difference existed among the income groups for Awareness, We conducted post hoc test or multiple comparison test to identify which among income groups differed significantly and the result is

exhibited in the Table: 1.20. The result of the analysis indicated that for Awareness, significant difference is observed between Below 30 years and Above 40 years. No significant difference was observed between Below 10,000 and other two groups. No difference was observed between 11,000 to 20,000 and 21,000 to 30,000. The difference between the groups is indicated by (*).

Table: 1.21. Types of family frequency and percentage levels of samples

Types of Family	Frequency	Percent
Joint	32	32.0
Nuclear	68	68.0
Total	100	100.0

Figure: 1.10.Types of Family wise frequency level of samples

An independent sample Z test were often used to compare the mean scores of variables the two different groups, that is, joint and nuclear families.

Hence a Z test was conducted, and the results are shown in Table: 1.21.

Table: 1.22 Means, standard deviation and z value for type of family

Variables	Types of family	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Z	P value
Awareness	Joint	32	27.38	8.09	0.872	0,385
	Nuclear	68	26.03	6.74		
Availability	Joint	32	26.72	9.60	1.139	0.257
	Nuclear	68	24.69	7.63		
Accessibility	Joint	32	26.53	8.68	1.443	0.152
	Nuclear	68	24.03	7.80		
Advantage	Joint	32	26.50	7.95	1.790	0.077
	Nuclear	68	23.75	6.78		

Interpretation

The result showed that no significant difference existed between for joint and nuclear families for all **Employment Status**

the variables as the p value in this case was more than 0.05.

Table: 1.23 Employment status frequency and percentage levels of samples

Employment status	Frequency	Percent
Employed	37	37.0
Unemployed	63	63.0
Total	100	100.0

Figure: 1.11 Employment status wise frequency level of samples

An independent sample Z test was often used to compare the mean scores. In this case, employment status was considered to be the independent

variable, which included two types, Employed and Unemployed. Hence a Z test was conducted, and the results are shown in Table: 1.23.

Table 1.24. Means, standard deviation and z value for employment status

Variable	Employment status	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Z	P value
Awareness	Employed	37	26.68	7.59	0.229	0.819
	Unemployed	63	26.33	7.00		
Availability	Employed	37	26.35	8.61	0.932	0.354
	Unemployed	63	24.75	8.14		
Accessibility	Employed	37	26.16	9.18	1.259	0,211
	Unemployed	63	24.05	7.42		
Advantage	Employed	37	25.46	8.16	0.876	0.383
	Unemployed	63	24.14	6.67		

Interpretation

The result showed that no significant difference existed between for Employed and

Unemployed respondents for the variables Awareness, Availability, Accessibility and Advantages as the p value in this case was more than 0.05.

Socio Economic Status

Table: 1.25 Socio economic status frequency and percentage levels of samples

Socioeconomic status	Frequency	Percent
Low	43	43.0
Middle	50	50.0
High	7	7.0
Total	100	100.0

Figure: 1.12 socioeconomic status wise frequency level of samples

A one sample analysis of variance was used to test hypotheses about means when there are three or more groups of one independent variable. In this case, Socio Economic Status was considered to be

the independent variable, which three groups (a) Low (b) Middle (c) High. So ANOVA was used to compare the mean scores of different groups and the result is exhibited in Table: 1.25.

Table: 1.26. Means, standard deviation and F value for socioeconomic status

Variables	Socio economic status	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	F	P value
Awareness	Low	43	25.12	7.71	1.843	0.164
	Middle	50	27.12	6.70		
	High	07	30.00	6.19		
Availability	Low	43	25.16	8.48	1.364	0.261
	Middle	50	24.80	8.09		
	High	07	30.29	8.46		
Accessibility	Low	43	25.24	7.55	0.673	0.512
	Middle	50	23.98	8.63		
	High	07	27.14	8.32		
Advantage	Low	43	25.93	7.06	3.436	0.036
	Middle	50	22.92	6.92		
	High	07	28.86	8.32		

Interpretation

The result of the ANOVA test, depicted in Table: 1. 26 revealed that the statistical value of p was more than 0.05 on the variables Awareness, Availability and Accessibility. So, we concluded that the mean score of

Awareness, Availability and Accessibility didn't differ with socio economic status. But in the case of Advantages significant difference was observed between Low, Middle and High school groups as the p value was less than 0.05.

Table: 1.27 Multiple comparison tests

Dependent Variable		Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	
Advantages	Low	Middle	3.01023*	1.471	0.043
		High	-2.927	2.884	0.313
	Middle	Low	-3.01023*	1.471	0.043
		High	-5.93714*	2.855	0.040
	High	Low	2.927	2.884	0.313
		Middle	5.93714*	2.855	0.040

The significant difference exist groups are indicated by (*).

Interpretation

Since the ANOVA test indicated that the significant difference existed among the Low, middle and high groups for Awareness, Availability and Accessibility, we conducted post hoc test or

multiple comparison test to identify which among socio economic groups differed significantly and the result is exhibited in the Table: 1. 27. The result of the analysis indicated that for Advantages, significant difference was observed between middle and low groups as well as middle and high groups. No difference was observed between low and high groups. The difference between the groups is indicated by (*).

Conclusion

The investigator planned to explore the status of implementing inclusive education schemes among SwIDs in Kerala. This descriptive survey study aimed to determine whether or not Kerala's school administrators, general educators, special educators, paraprofessionals, and parents of students with intellectual disabilities were aware of, had access to or benefited from services for SwIDs. Current studies on inclusive education schemes and support to uphold meaningful reintegration of SwIDs are thought to benefit from the outcomes of this research. It anticipates that future studies will build on and expand upon the present work to the point where its limitations are no longer an issue.

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